

MICROBIAL CONTAMINATION OF UNIVERSITY OF PORT HARCOURT SHUTTLE DRIVER'S PALMS AND STEERING WHEEL

***Akomah-Abadaïke, O.N and Macaulay, O.G.**

University of Port Harcourt, School of Science laboratory Technology, Microbiology Technology Option PMB 5323 Choba Port Harcourt Rivers State, Nigeria.

ORCID: *<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7043-3643>

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Abstract: Commercial drivers interact with so many persons in a day and do cash transactions, which expose them to wide range of bacteria and fungi. This study evaluated the microbial load of Uniport shuttle drivers' palms and their vehicle steering wheels. Total heterotrophic bacteria and fungi were enumerated and identified using standard laboratory techniques. The antimicrobial sensitivity and resistance pattern was also evaluated. The results in range obtained were; palms THBC $2 \times 10^3 - 2.0 \times 10^4$ cfu/mL, and TFC $1.5 \times 10^2 - 1.35 \times 10^4$ cfu/mL, while steering wheels THBC $2.0 \times 10^3 - 1.25 \times 10^4$ cfu/mL, and TFC $1.5 \times 10^2 - 1.21 \times 10^4$ cfu/mL. The diversity of bacterial and fungal isolates, and their percentage occurrence frequency included bacteria; *Propionibacterium* spp. (25%), *Bacillus* spp. (5%), *Staphylococcus* spp. (17.5%), *Corynebacterium* spp. (7.5%), *Streptococcus* spp. (10%), *Escherichia coli* (5%), *Klebsiella* spp. (5%), and fungi *Rhodotorula* spp. (27.5%), *Penicillium italicum* (37.5%), *Aspergillus niger* (15%), *Penicillium expansum* (15%), *Candida albican* (10%), *Malassezia* spp. (12.5%) and *Fusarium* spp. (22.5%). The palms of commercial vehicles' drivers and the steering wheels of their vehicles share similar bacterial and fungal diversity. These bacteria and fungi are mostly members of the normal flora of the skin, which can be pathogenic if the skin is breached or they gain access to the mucosal surfaces.

Keywords: Commercial drivers, Steering wheels, *Propionibacterium* spp, *Penicillium italicum*, antimicrobial resistance.

1. Introduction

The COVID 19 pandemic emphasis the important of hand washing hygienic (Mutters and Warnes, 2019). Studies show this help in reducing microbial load on the hands (Mutters and Warnes, 2019), especially the drying method employed (Mutters and Warnes, 2019). The presence of pathogenic organisms on the hands and steering wheels of commercial driver is important since it can lead to transmission of such pathogen to commuter (Abiose, 2019; Umeanaeto et al., 2021).

The multi-drug resistance problem laid bear the important to check-mate the spread of pathogenic organisms (Mutters and Warnes, 2019); which can lead to community associated infection.

In the University of Port Harcourt, Choba, Nigeria, most students and staff commute to the University via the shutter buses and taxis. They come in contact with the drivers through exchange of pleasantries and transport fee (Osei et al., 2021). Since some of these microbes are pathogenic, there is the likelihood that most causes of the

diseases among commercial vehicle drivers and public transport users in Nigeria might be attributed to steering wheel surface contamination. Hence, there is a need to undertake this study to identify the type of microorganisms involved; this study identified and enumerate the bacterial and fungal contaminants on Uniport shuttle drivers' palms and steering wheels. Its specific objectives are (i) enumeration of bacterial and fungal genera on palms and steering wheels. (ii) Evaluation of similarities and variations between isolates from palms and steering wheel. (iii) Determination of antibiotic susceptibility test.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Sample collection

Samples were collected using sterile swabs soaked in 0.1% saline solution. One swab was used for a driver's palm and another for the steering wheel. The swab's part containing the wool (sample) was aseptically cut into Bijou bottle or tube (a swab per tube) of 10mL 0.1% saline solution; one swab per tube. Then the swabs were labelled properly and taken immediately to the laboratory for analysis. P1- P30 for drivers' palm and S1 -S30 for driver's steering wheel.

2.2 Isolation and identification of bacteria and fungi from drivers' palms and their vehicle steering wheels

A modified method of isolation as demonstrated by Osei *et al.* (2021) was adopted. Each tube containing swab samples (10mL of 0.1% saline water) was vortexed to ensure a mixture of the sample. A tenfold serial dilution was prepared by transferring 1mL of the homogenized sample to 9mL diluents (distilled water). From dilution 10^2 , a 0.1mL aliquot was spread-plated on nutrient agar (NA) and Potato dextrose agar (PDA) media. Then NA plates were incubated for 24h at 37°C and PDA plates incubated for 72-96h at 30°C . Bacterial isolates were identified by microscopy and biochemical characterization, while fungal isolates were identified by plate morphology and microscopic features.

2.3 Determination of frequency of occurrence of bacterial and fungal genera on palms and steering wheels

The occurrence frequency of each species was calculated using the formula below

$$\text{Frequency (\%)} = \frac{\text{Number of samples contaminated with a species or genus}}{\text{Total number of samples}} \times 100$$

2.4 Determination of similarities and variations between isolates from palms and steering wheels

As demonstrated by Osei *et al.* (2021), the bacterial isolates from drivers' palms and steering wheels of vehicles were compared with each other, likewise, the fungal isolates from drivers' palms and steering wheels of vehicles were compared.

2.5 Antibiotic susceptibility test

The purpose of this experiment was to employ Kirby-Bauer disc diffusion, following the methodology described by Reyam-Abdul *et al.* (2022). The bacterial isolates were tested against Gram positive and Gram-negative antibiotics. The process began with freshly prepared Nutrient Agar that had been autoclaved at 121°C for 15 minutes. After that, it was left to set and dry. Next, 5ml of sterile distilled water was added to the test isolate, and its turbidity was adjusted to 0.5 MacFarland standard. Using a sterile swab stick that had been dipped in the inoculum, a streak was aseptically applied to the surface of the agar. Finally, a sterile wire loop was used to place the antibiotic-impregnated test disc to the agar. To facilitate the antibiotic disc's diffusion into the agar, it is touched. One day was spent incubating the plates at 37 degrees Celsius. The antimicrobial susceptibility test's

interpretive chart was used to classify the zones of inhibition as sensitive or resistant, and the clear zones of inhibition were measured in millimetres (mm) (CLSI, 2020).

3. Results and Discussion

Figure 1: Frequency of occurrence of bacterial isolates from Uniport commercial drivers' palm and their steering wheels

Figure 2: Frequency of occurrence of fungal isolates from Uniport commercial drivers' palm and their steering wheels

Samples	P (CFU/mL)	S (CFU/mL)
	Counts × 10 ² cfu/mL	
1	115.5	125
2	70	20
3	98	15.5
4	128.5	30
5	NG	TFTC
6	90	13.5
7	200	60.5
8	TFTC	TNTC
9	22	TFTC
10	8.5	TNTC
11	110	90
12	69	TFTC
13	82	22.5
14	95	30
15	64	TFTC
16	116.5	TFTC
17	89.5	44
18	27.5	72.5
19	61.5	70
	79.5	34
20		

Table 1: Mean Total Bacteria Count from drivers' palms and steering wheels

Table 2: Similarities and variations between isolates diversities on drivers palms and their steering wheels

Isolates	Presence on palms	Presence on steering wheels
<i>Propionibacterium</i> spp.	+	+
<i>Bacillus</i> spp.	+	-
<i>Staphylococcus</i> spp.	+	+
<i>Corynebacterium</i> spp.	+	+
<i>Streptococcus</i> spp.	+	+
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	+	+
<i>Klebsiella</i> spp.	-	+
<i>Rhodotorula</i> spp.	+	+
<i>Penicillium italicum</i>	+	+
<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	+	+
<i>Penicillium expansum</i>	+	+
<i>Candida albican</i>	+	+
<i>Malassezia</i> spp.	+	+
<i>Fusarium</i> spp.	+	+

Table 3. Antibiotics sensitivity of Gram’s positive bacterial isolates from drivers’ palm and steering swabs

Isolate codes/microorganisms	S	AS	BA	E	TE	CF	CP	OF	LE	GM	CX	RO
	Zones of Inhibition in mm											
P1(<i>Propionibacterium</i> spp)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
P2(<i>Bacillus</i> spp)	0	8	0	0	0	0	9	8	12	0	0	0

P4(Staphylococcus spp)	4	0	0	7	0	0	0	0	13	9	5	19
P5(Corynebacterium spp)	14	10	20	20	16	14	20	20	22	22	22	22
P6(Streptococcus spp)	0	0	0	11	0	0	6	8	0	0	7	6
P7(Propionibacterium spp)	7	0	8	0	0	10	5	0	0	0	0	10
P8(Staphylococcus spp)	9	0	0	11	0	0	0	0	18	22	9	26
P13(Corynebacterium spp)	16	12	24	22	19	17	23	23	26	26	25	27
P17(Bacillus spp)	0	11	0	0	0	0	7	12	10	0	0	0
S21(Streptococcus spp)	0	0	0	9	0	0	8	9	0	0	6	5

Key: S; streptomycin, AS; ampicilin/sulbactam, BA; Co-trimoxazole, CF; Cefotaxime, E; erythromycin, CP; ciprofloxacin, TE; tetracycline, OF; ofloxacin, GM; gentamycin, LE; levofloxacin, RO; roxythromycin, CX; cefoxitin

Table 4. Antibiotics sensitivity of Gram’s negative bacterial isolates from drivers’ palm and steering swabs

Isolate codes	TE	AS	BA	CE	PT	C	CP	CR	LE	OF	GM	AT
	Zones of Inhibition in mm											
P12(Escherichia coli)	10	12	15	22	17	14	22	24	30	32	22	40
S26(Escherichia coli)	24	24	19	24	14	0	24	24	30	24	4	36
S27(Klesiella spp)	11	20	18	0	0	0	0	22	30	22	6	20
S29(Klesiella spp)	8	6	28	0	0	0	0	6	26	20	28	18

Key: CE; cephradine, PT; piperacillin/tazobactam, C; chloramphenicol, CR; ceftriaxone, AT; azithromycin,

The total heterotrophic bacteria count (THBC) of bacterial isolates from the palms of Uniport commercial drivers ranged from 2.2×10^3 - 2.0×10^4 CFU/ml. This result is lower than the THBC range $2.1 - 3.77 \times 10^6$ CFU/ml reported by Sagay *et al.* (2022) in a similar study. The difference in range could be attributed to factors such as location, personal hygiene of the individuals enrolled for the study and their history of antibiotic use. The THBC of bacterial isolates from the steering wheels of Uniport commercial vehicles ranged from 2.0×10^3 - 1.25×10^4 CFU/ml. This result is similar to the THBC range of $1.97 - 2.41 \times 10^4$ cfu/mL reported by Akinnibosun *et al.*

(2024) in their study of “microbiological assessment of car doors and steering wheels at Benue State University, Makurdi: Public health implications.”

The diversity of bacteria and fungi from Uniport commercial drivers’ palm and their vehicle’s steering wheels included *Propionibacterium* spp., *Bacillus* spp., *Staphylococcus* spp., *Corynebacterium* spp., *Streptococcus* spp., *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella* spp., *Rhodotorula* spp., *Penicillium italicum*, *Aspergillus niger*, *Penicillium expansum*, *Candida albican*, *Malassezia* spp. and *Fusarium* spp. Most of these bacteria and fungi have been listed as part of the microbiome of the human skin; *Propionibacterium* spp., *Bacillus* spp., *Staphylococcus* spp., *Corynebacterium* spp., *Streptococcus* spp., *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella* spp. (Byrd *et al.*, 2018, Cundell, 2018), *Rhodotorula* spp., (Bay *et al.*, 2020), *P. italicum* and *expansum* (Cespedes *et al.*, 2022), *Aspergillus niger* (Oruko *et al.*, 2019), *Candia albican* (Lopes and Lionakis, 2022) and *Malassezia* spp. (Nowicka and Nawrot, 2019), whereas *Fusarium* spp. is a pathogenic environmental fungi (Hof, 2020). These microorganisms though mostly microflora of the human skin (palm), if they gain access to internal tissues and organs, they become pathogenic. The percentage of occurrence frequency of the bacterial isolates revealed that *Propionibacterium* spp. had the highest frequency followed by *Staphylococcus* spp. This result corroborates with the report by McLaughlin *et al.* (2019) who list *Propionibacterium* spp., *Staphylococcus* spp., and *Streptococcus* spp. as the major residents of normal skin flora.

The percentage of occurrence frequency of the fungal isolates revealed that *Penicillium italicum* had the highest frequency followed by *Rhodotorula* spp. This result corroborates with the result of Madsen *et al.* (2020) who reported *Penicillium* spp. as the major fungi human is exposed to. This result agrees with Jarros *et al.* (2018) and Cespedes *et al.* (2022) who in separate studies reported *Rhodotorula* spp. as one of the most common fungi on human skin. Although, *Fusarium* spp. was not part of normal flora of the skin, the fungi were the third in occurrence frequency. This was because *Fusarium* spp. spores are very common in the air and settles on any surface (palms or steering wheels), where they grow very fast under favourable conditions of moisture, nutrients, temperature etc.

In terms of similarity between isolates from palms and steering wheels, all fungi isolated from drivers’ palm were also, isolated from their steering wheels; whereas in the bacterial isolates, *Bacillus* spp. was only found on drivers’ palm and *Klebsiella* spp. was only found on steering wheels. There were more similarities because contact between palm and steering wheels facilitated transfer and sharing of microorganism between the two surfaces. The exception of *Bacillus* and *Klebsiella* spp. could be from contact with other objects or dust settlements carrying the bacteria.

The antibiotic sensitivity tests showed that *Propionibacterium* spp. were most resistant to the antibiotics among the Gram’s positive bacteria. This result corroborates with the result by Nair and Kollanoor Johny (2018) who reported multi-drug resistance by *Propionibacterium* spp. *Corynebacterium* spp. were susceptible to all the antibiotics. This does not agree with the result of Neemuchwala *et al.* (2018) who reported both susceptibility and resistance among species of *Corynebacterium*. Other Gram’s positive isolates were susceptible and resistance to different antibiotics; this is similar to the results by Ahmed *et al.* (2022). The sensitive test of the two Gram’s negative isolates showed that *E. coli* (P12, S26) was susceptible to all the antibiotics, while *Klebsiella* spp. (S27, S29) were resistant to four antibiotics which included cephadrine, piperacillin/tazobactam, chloramphenicol and ciprofloxacin. The susceptibility displayed by *E. coli* in this study disagrees with Poirel *et*

al. (2018), who reported *E. coli* as an antibiotic-resistant developing bacteria. Resistance to antibiotics is induced mostly by previous exposure to the antibiotic or other agents.

CONCLUSION

The palms of commercial vehicles' drivers and the steering wheels of their vehicles share similar bacterial and fungal diversity. These bacteria and fungi are mostly members of the normal flora of the skin, which can be pathogenic if the skin is breached or they gain access to the mucosal surfaces.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors do not report any financial or personal connections with other persons or organizations, which might negatively affect the contents of this publication and/or claim authorship rights to this publication.

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